

Fruth Wetland Project, Seneca County (41.13147, -83.36540)

Since construction in 2021, the primary known nutrient benefit of the Fruth Wetland Project has been its runoff prevention due to conversion from an agricultural field and removal as a nutrient, preventing 0.7 lbs phosphorus export per acre each year. Otherwise, the Project has operated as an isolated depressional wetland. Precipitation events and seasonal groundwater table fluctuations are the primary hydrologic drivers at this Project. This lack of direct system inputs and outputs likely limited both the nutrient inputs to the Project and the ability of researchers to assess the nutrient benefit of this Project. Soils have capacity to sorb phosphate if and when water and nutrient inputs are received to the Project.

Surface Water Flow

The hydrology of this Project is passively managed. The Project has 10 acres of restored wetland and consists of four wetland pools that connect to Wolf Creek in the southeast via shallow groundwater. A hydrologic event at this Project is defined as a storm event in which the depressional pools receive runoff.

Nutrient Retention

Converted Farmfield Area	Phosphorus Loss Prevented Annually	
	Per Acre	Total (Mean ± SD)
10 acres	0.7 lbs	12 ± 8 lbs

Enhancement Considerations*

The following practices may yield increased nutrient removal in this or similar isolated wetland Projects or could be accounted for in future site selection:

- Expanding the amount of stormwater runoff the Project receives by increasing either connection to upland drainage or connection to subsurface tile drainage on the southern border of the Project could improve its nutrient retention potential.
- Consider improvements such as allowing direct tile inflow from the southern bordering field or digging the pools deeper to increase groundwater connectivity. These alterations would allow more input to Pool 1 following storm events and for Pool 1 to retain water for a greater portion of the year, as well as allowing researchers to collect more water samples from this location.
- Assess parcel footprint for the ability to capture tile drain, stream, or ditch water inputs, in addition to precipitation, to optimize nutrient input potential (i.e., connectivity).

*All considerations are based on the best available science at this time, and all recommended items may not be feasible given physical constraints, resource limitations, and broader management goals.